

POLYANILINE/CELLULOSE CONDUCTIVE COMPOSITE BY SELF-ASSEMBLY OF SILANE COUPLING AGENT

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1 Introduction

Microbial cellulose, so-called bacterial cellulose (BC) has been attracting more attention than ever. It has an outstanding ability to hold water and has young's modulus which is comparable to that of aluminum. In addition, its biodegradability and environmental-friendliness in process are also the reasons. Recently, a lot of research has been treating this bio-based material, suggesting of the possible uses for such as electronics and film industry. In this study, polyaniline (PANI), one of conductive polymers, was synthesized onto a BC surface attained by a self-assembly (SA) of a silane coupling agent.

In this study, the synthesized PANI/SA-BC composite had a good electrically conductivity around 1.52 S/cm achieved by a dense packing of PANI on an arrayed layer of a silane coupling agent on BC surface.

2 Experimental

2.1 Preparation of substrate

(Synthesis of Bacterial Cellulose)

Glucoacetobacter xylinum was statically cultured in HS (Hestrin and Schramm) medium. After sterilized at 121 °C for 1.5 hours, the medium was supposed to support a growth of 3 day-old active bacteria cells. The flask containing the medium and cells was kept at 30 °C and the growth of the cell was allowed only for 10 days. This raw BC pellicle was washed thoroughly with de-ionized water followed by washing with 1 M sodium hydroxide solution. After

removing cells left on the cellulose, it was kept in 20 % alcohol solution below 15 °C.

2.2 Chemicals

3-APTMS (Aminopropyltrimethoxysilane) was purchased from Merck chemicals (Germany). Glacial acetic acid and methanol are from Samchun Chemical Co. (Korea). Monomer aniline and ammonium persulfate as initiator were purchased from Duksan Pure Chemical Co. (Korea). Hydrochloric acid for a doping agent as well as solvent and chloroform as an organic solvent were supplied from Samchun Chemical Co. (Korea). All starting materials were reagent grade and used as purchased.

2.3 Instrumentation

Functional groups on the substrate were investigated by Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) analysis. The IR spectra were recorded using FT/IR-6100 (JASCO, Japan) equipped with a Miracle accessory, an attenuated total reflectance (ATR). The specimens were analyzed over the range from 4000 to 600 cm⁻¹ with a spectrum resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. All spectra were averaged over 30 scans.

To evaluate changes of the nature of surface chemistry, video contact angle analyzer (VCA) Phoenix 300 (Surface & Electro-Optics Co., Korea) was used. A series of pictures were taken in few seconds after a water droplet was deposited on the substrate at room temperature. The VCA registered the angles on both sides of the droplet.

The morphology of the composites was observed by field emission scanning electron microscopy, SUPRA 55VP (Carl Zeiss, Germany) at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV. All the samples were pre-coated with a homogeneous platinum layer by ion sputtering to eliminate electron charging.

A 4-probe conductivity equipment (Changmin Tech, Korea) was used for the conductivity tests. All specimens were well-dried and have flat surface when used.

2.4 Procedure

2.4.1 Silanisation of Bacterial Cellulose surface

Among several organosilanes, 3-APTMS was selected. As suggested in Figure 1, aniline monomer can be absorbed physically/chemically on an amine-terminated cellulose surface [1]. 1 % w/w 3-APTMS was dissolved in methanol and the solution was subjected to be stirred for 2 hours at 60 °C. When the temperature was elevated, BC was to be soaked within the solution under stirring condition. When the reaction finished, the BC was taken out of the solution followed by washing with de-ionized water. A heat treatment afterwards matters so much [2]. The modified BC was placed in a dryer which was set above 100 °C for 1 hour for a further formation of polysiloxane between silanol and hydroxyl groups of cellulose.

Fig. 1. Ideal diagram of self-assembly of 3-APTMS on BC.

2.4.2 Polymerization of aniline

After silanisation, slightly wet BC was immersed in 1 M hydrochloric acid containing 0.1 mol of aniline monomer for 10 minutes. If silanisation above was done properly, a well-ordered amine moiety protruding out of BC surface would be a site to which aniline monomer can get close. BC experienced in-situ polymerization initiated by 0.025 mol of oxidant, ammonium persulfate (APS). This polymerization lasted for 2 hours below 10 °C. The BC colored deep greenish was washed with de-ionized water in order to eliminate unreacted aniline and lastly with 1 M hydrochloric acid for doping effect. A dedoping process for confirming a possibility of an application to pH sensor was performed with 1 M sodium hydroxide solution.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 FTIR Analysis

It is reported that some possible structures instead of self-assembly have been reported because of high reactivity of amine [3]. As shown in Figure 2, which compares SA-BC with raw BC, a deformed amine peak was observed at 1465 and 1589 cm^{-1} . Moreover, a Si–O–Si bond peak at 1099 cm^{-1} also appeared clearly due to the formation of polysiloxane network, which matched the results of some previous research [4, 5].

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectrum of raw BC and SA-BC of 1800 – 800 cm^{-1} region.

3.2 Contact Angle

The changes in contact angle with following process were shown in Table 1. When a droplet of water is deposited, an air-dried BC shows a hydrophilic character because of its abundant hydroxyl groups. After silanisation on the surface followed by heat treatment, the trend was changed into rather hydrophobic. If amine groups of 3-APTMS are arrayed by self assembly, it is preferable to show hydrophilicity due to a formation of hydrogen bond to water. For verifying the potential of conductive cellulose film as pH sensor, the process of doping and dedoping by hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide respectively was applied and Table 1 indicates the result.

Table 1. Contact angle and conductivity

(ES : Emeraldine Salt, EB : Emeraldine Base)

Sample name	Contact angle (°)	Conductivity (S/cm)
Pristine BC	35.4 ± 0.8	-
APTMS/BC	75	-
PANI(ES)/APTMS/BC	< 5	1.52
PANI(EB)/APTMS/BC	60 ± 5	< 1x10 ⁻³

3.3 Conductivity

A conductivity of the composite was confirmed by 4-point probe equipment and mentioned in Table 1. Compared to PANI/BC without any surface modifications, the conductivity of PANI/SA-BC showed around 1.52 S/cm. This PANI/SA-BC had higher conductivity than the composite which had conductivity of 0.034 S/cm. This was composed of polyacrylamide (PAAm) and PANI reported by Dai *et al* [6]. The conductivity of PANI/BC composite without any surface modification was about 0.163 S/cm.

This can be explained by an arranged surface obtained by 3-APTMS, which aniline monomer attaches to readily. This regularity brought efficient charge transfer between PANI. It is also assumed that the composite synthesized by self-assembly has relatively more nucleation sites compared to conventional solution polymerization of aniline.

Immobilized amine on BC surface can contribute to decrease the possibility of polymerization happening in bulk solution.

3.4 Morphology

For the composites obtained after drying at room temperature, FE-SEM images reveal that PANI was attached very well on each BC nanofiber (see Figure 3, bottom). Thanks to high surface area of BC, this composite could intensify the conductivity.

Fig. 3. FE-SEM image of BC (top, × 50,000) and PANI/SA-BC (bottom, × 50,000).

4 Conclusion

A small amount of a silane coupling agent was able to prepare a partly self-assembled surface. From an analysis of FTIR spectrum, certain peaks meaning Si-O-Si bond and amine groups appeared after heat treatment. The synthesis of conducting polymer on an arrayed surface made conductivity increase up to 1.52 S/cm. A contact angle was changed depending

on pH and it enabled us to decide whether a coupling agents work well.

This composite can be applied to pH sensor, electrical devices, bioactuator and so on.

References

- [1] J. Li, L. Zhu, Y. Wu, Y. Harima, A. Zhang, and H. Tang, "Hybrid composites of conductive polyaniline and nanocrystalline titanium oxide prepared via self-assembling and graft polymerization". *Polymer*, Vol. 47, No. 21, pp. 7361-7367, 2006.
- [2] A. G. Cunha, and A. Gandini, "Turning polysaccharides into hydrophobic materials: a critical review. Part 1. Cellulose". *Cellulose*, Vol. 17, No. 5, pp. 875-889, Oct, 2010.
- [3] C. Chiang, H. Ishida, and J. Koenig, "The structure of [gamma]-aminopropyltriethoxysilane on glass surfaces". *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, Vol. 74, No. 2, pp. 396-404, 1980.
- [4] M. Abdelmouleh, S. Boufi, A. ben Salah, M. N. Belgacem, and A. Gandini, "Interaction of silane coupling agents with cellulose". *Langmuir*, Vol. 18, No. 8, pp. 3203-3208, Apr, 2002.
- [5] M. Abdelmouleh, S. Boufi, M. N. Belgacem, A. P. Duarte, A. Ben Salah, and A. Gandini, "Modification of cellulosic fibres with functionalised silanes: development of surface properties". *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, Vol. 24, No. 1, pp. 43-54, Feb, 2004.
- [6] T. Y. Dai, X. T. Qing, J. Wang, C. Shen, and Y. Lu, "Interfacial polymerization to high-quality polyacrylamide/polyaniline composite hydrogels". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 70, No. 3, pp. 498-503, 2010.